

Renewable energy community

Lessons learned and recommendations from POCITYF's use case in Valverde, Évora

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Renewable energy communities (RECs) and Collective self-consumption schemes (CSCs) are key instruments to empower citizens and municipalities. They enable **local energy sharing** and foster active participation, contributing to reducing energy costs, promoting sustainability, and even **fighting energy poverty**.

Under the POCITYF project, the initiatives in Valverde and Sonae are examples of how innovation and community engagement can help improve **local energy positivity** while also serving as examples of how these solutions can be replicated on a broad national level.

Key points:

Collective self-consumption fosters local energy sharing and citizen empowerment, while also potentially mitigating energy poverty situations.

Scaleable design allows future members, assets, better use of local resources and increase local energy positivity.

Regulatory complexity remains a major barrier to their implementation in Portugal, despite the multiple benefits.

POCITYF framework

The **POCITYF project** is a European funded project aimed at delivering a set of **positive energy blocks** to transform cities' urban environments with a strong emphasis on cultural and historical protected areas. The goal is to make them more inclusive, sustainable and safer for their citizens. To achieve this, the POCITYF framework has been applied to **two lighthouse cities, Évora and Alkmaar**, and some of the tested solutions have been replicated in other 6 fellow cities all over Europe: **Granada, Bari, Ioannina, Celje, Upjest and Hvidovre**.

Évora Lighthouse City and Valverde

Évora hosts multiple demonstration areas distributed across three distinct positive energy blocks (**PEBs**), where its innovative solutions will be validated. **Valverde**, a village located roughly 12 km from Évora, is part of the PEB2 pilot, extending the project's impact beyond the city and into peri-urban communities.

Technical Overview

The **Valverde pilot** demonstrates the operation of REC, with key innovative elements:

Each participating household is equipped with a 1.5 kWp rooftop PV system, ensuring local generation of clean electricity. Each will also test Battery Energy Storage Systems, enabling storage of excess electrical energy generated from the photovoltaic systems for future usage, enhancing local flexibility and self-consumption.

The REC is designed to remain open and expandable, allowing new members to join with or without their own local production.

During the project's monitoring phase, a peer-to-peer (P2P) trading market is implemented among community members. Results and insights from the P2P process will feed into Portuguese regulatory developments, mainly POCITYF's regulatory sandbox pilot with ERSE on P2P trading and dynamic sharing coefficient methodologies.¹

The REC is equipped with **digital tools** to help simplify operations and ensure transparent and secure management of the community. These tools support the monitoring of the community's energy flows, provide estimations of energy sharing costs incurred, and establish P2P trading or the configuration of energy-sharing methodologies.

¹ [ERSE's Pilot projects approved under the Self-Consumption Regulation \[in Portuguese\]](#).

Benefits and lessons learned

Benefits

- Energy communities allow consumers and citizens to have **more power**.

Lessons

- The **regulatory process** is still very long and (sometimes) complicated/complex.
- Adaptations to the installation and energy assets must be planned before the REC creation process starts in order to avoid unnecessary communication with the granting entity. The adaptation can be technical (e.g., the changing of the member's energy meter for a smart meter) or regulatory (e.g., the generation unit is not correctly registered on the granting entity). This leads to **extensive due diligence** on the buildings that are supposed to form the REC or CSC.

Conclusions and Recommendations for policymakers

Current Portuguese regulatory processes for establishing RECs or CSC schemes are extended and detailed, therefore can seem complex and time-consuming, creating barriers for implementation. Streamlining these bureaucratic processes and **providing clear guidelines to promoters and citizens** will help communities establish and operate RECs more efficiently, fostering a wider adoption of these schemes.

Improving citizens' access to information, funding and technical expertise is also essential if these mechanisms are to be successfully rolled out. Policymakers should consider **dedicated financial incentives, grants, and advisory programmes** to empower local communities to promote, develop and maintain local energy-sharing initiatives.

Promoting the widespread use of secure and interoperable digital tools in these contexts enables **more transparent monitoring and governance processes** (nowadays, the options for management tools are paid, since they were developed by private companies). These tools can also enable **more dynamic energy-sharing models** (and even allow trading of energy between members by themselves, in a peer-to-peer trading scheme) supporting the evolution of flexible and decentralized citizen-centric energy systems.

Encouraging secure, intuitive platforms and dashboards helps build trust among participating members and organizations. These digital solutions make **information more accessible**, simplify administrative and operational tasks, and reduce burdens that often discourage participation.

They also strengthen communication channels between key stakeholders (e.g., DSOs, community members, and managing entities), ensuring **smoother coordination**.

Integrating RECs into wider national energy systems' strategic planning and frameworks is equally important, ensuring consistent support measures and reinforces policy coherence. Recognising RECs as key instruments for promoting decentralised, flexible, and energy-positive centres – be it in urban areas, rural territories, or historically or culturally protected cities –, policy and regulation can contribute directly to a **more resilient and positive energy transition**. Furthermore, RECs and CSC must be inserted in energy markets with a wider scope than only the distribution grid and the respective DSO.

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